

Systematic Review into how health promotion interventions influence university student health

ABSTRACT

Background

Health within university student populations is very much a subjective concept, being multifactorial in nature; consisting of various interrelated aspects which can be broadly grouped into a number of specific topic areas: health care access, mental health, sexual health, physical activity/nutrition and substance use. Previous studies and reviews have examined the various aspects of the health of university students in isolation but few have attempted to construct a synergistic narrative.

Objectives

To characterize student perceptions in regard to health and whether health promotion interventions have a positive or negative effect.

Data sources

The following databases were searched: CINAHL Plus with Full Text, MEDLINE, PubMed and ProQuest Central. Smaller numbers of articles were located using PsycARTICLES, ERIC and SPORTDiscus with Full Text. A small number of articles were also obtained from bibliographic searching of database sourced articles.

Study eligibility criteria

To be included in this review studies must have been written post-2005. Only studies from the UK, Australia, USA, Canada and New Zealand were included. Studies without a survey element were excluded.

Participants

Participants consisted of undergraduate students, combinations of undergraduates and postgraduates, international students, multi-university student samples, samples composed of staff and students, university healthcare providers and patients students enrolled in specific subjects and comparisons between students with differing characteristics.

Interventions

Targeted interventions focussing on members of a particular student subpopulation and on-campus general or condition-specific social marketing campaigns.

Study appraisal and synthesis methods

A standardized electronic data extraction form was utilized to record study information on study design, participants, sample size, source, setting, response rate, risk of bias, result, conclusions and limitations. Studies were analyzed using narrative analysis to develop thematic consistencies based upon intervention type, health area and research design.

Results

It was observed that an overall decline in levels of health takes places beginning with commencement of undergraduate study and that a large proportion of student health issues have their roots in mental health as a mediating factor. Peer group membership and campus environment also appear to play a major role in propensity toward engaging in healthy behavior or not. Where health promotion intervention programs are undertaken on-campus the overall impact on health appears to be positive.

Limitations

Data within this study is analyzed using non-statistical methods and by a single reviewer only. Additionally, a large number of observational studies are included which may limit overall generalizability of findings.

Conclusions

University students are a population at increased risk of poor health with mental health acting as a mediating factor affecting risk in relation to other areas of health. Therefore, health promotion programs need to be better planned to address multiple health issues within a single intervention format.

Implications of key findings

University students and other target populations need to be consulted during the intervention planning process so that a sense of ownership can be developed, facilitating self-efficacy and improving the overall effectiveness of health promotion efforts. Moreover, approaches to student health research need to be re-aligned so that the specific areas of student health are no longer viewed in isolation.

BACKGROUND

Description of the Condition

Health is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as “a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. It is very much a subjective concept, and is composed of multiple determinants. Health within student populations is multifactorial in nature (Kwan et al. 2013). It is possible to group student-specific health conditions into a number of general themes. Namely, healthcare access, mental health, sexual health, physical activity/nutrition and substance use. Within these categories mental health appears to be a major determinant. Furthermore, interaction across and within these different areas appears to influence propensity toward the later development of chronic disease and the degree to which healthy lifestyle behaviors are adopted later in life (Holt et al. 2015; Kwan et al. 2013; Lombardi & Dupain 2014).

The relatively closed nature of a university means they are able to exert considerable environmental influence on health from both structural and organizational perspective (Holt et al. 2015). Universities constitute ideal settings in which to undertake health promotion due to their population density (Holt et al. 2015). However, where university infrastructure is not optimally geared towards promoting health a negative effect on overall population health measures may be observed (Holt et al. 2015). Within this setting interplay between environment and individual health is complex with culture and personal behavior also playing a role (Holt et al. 2015).

Description of the intervention

Health promotion interventions are often implemented within the university setting, both as a means to improve population health and to undertake research (Ehrhardt et al. 2006). University student populations tend to be diverse, but concentrated within a relatively small area making the potential impacts of well planned interventions quite dramatic in terms of the degree of health improvement observed (Holt et al. 2015; Kwan et al. 2013; Lombardi & Dupain 2014). Interventions may take numerous forms including physical activity programs, public education campaigns and improvements to campus health services (Brown et al. 2014; Carmack et al. 2016).

Why it is important to undertake this review

In the past the various discrete areas of student health have been viewed in isolation rather than treating them as component parts of a wider interrelated health concept (Dawson et al. 2007). Studies have previously gathered data on various determinants of

health and risk factors in relation to student populations (Dawson et al. 2007). However, to date none have attempted to contextualize student health across multiple thematic areas in an attempt to establish the multifactorial nature of the health of university students. This needs to be done in order to aid the planning process for undertaking health promotion interventions, so that programs can be targeted to improve multiple aspects of health within a single intervention. Thus benefiting more people in a shorter space of time, in a more resource efficient manner.

Objectives

This study aims to characterize student perceptions in regard to health and whether health promotion interventions positively or negatively influence levels of health within this population group. The main objective is to establish whether the various factors influencing student health outcomes are interrelated.

Research Question

The **population** group under study are university students experiencing **interventions** designed to measure or improve health, with no intervention or a standard existing advice or approaches to treatment functioning as the **comparison**. The **outcome** of interest is whether health promotion interventions positively or negatively influence health and foster behavior change within the campus environment which functions as our **setting**. Therefore our research question is:

“Do campus based health promotion interventions positively or negatively influence student health?”

Hypothesis

H_0 : Campus based health promotion interventions positively influence student health.

H_1 : Campus based health promotion interventions have no effect upon student health.

METHODS

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of studies

Included are randomized controlled trials and observational studies with individual or cluster designs which are category specific to healthcare access, mental health, sexual health, physical activity/nutrition or substance use within student populations.

Types of participants

Considered were studies taking place within a university, college or other post-secondary setting composed of both domestic and international students.

Types of intervention

- Targeted interventions focussing on members of a particular subpopulation, such as domestic or international students, athletes or non-athletes, members of certain student societies or members deemed to be at higher risk of certain health conditions
- On campus general or condition-specific social marketing campaigns whether community wide or aimed at specific student subpopulations

Control interventions

- No intervention
- Survey based studies gathering general health information only
- Studies with open enrollment from the entire student body, with or without randomization

Types of outcome measure

The following outcome measures were of interest:

- Self-reported improvement in health as a result of intervention
- Decrease in risky behavior, as appropriate to health category
- Increase in health literacy as a result of intervention

Search Strategy

Databases

Choice of databases from which to source literature were finalised during the initial scoping review based upon availability of articles, relevance and we quality if the studies available in terms of where they could be placed upon the hierarchy of evidence. Specific databases used to conduct the literature search were: ProQuest Central. Smaller numbers of articles were located using PsycARTICLES, ERIC and SPORTDiscus with Full Text.

Searching other resources

The bibliographies of all included studies were reviewed to identify additional relevant citations.

Keywords and search terms

Search terms, database and numbers of results obtained for each query were recorded in a spreadsheet. Where database compatibility was available, boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT) were utilized to better focus the search when using multiple search terms. Truncation was not used.

Selection criteria

To be included in this review studies must have been written post-2005. Only studies from countries within the Anglosphere (UK, Australia, USA, Canada and New Zealand) were included in this review in an effort to control for cultural differences and because of the similarity of the higher education systems within these countries. Studies without a survey element were excluded from the analysis, as one of the primary aims of this review was to assess students' subjective perceptions in regard to the concept of health.

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

Studies were selected using the single reviewer method, with strict adherence to the inclusion criteria. All titles and abstracts were read, and obviously irrelevant studies were eliminated. Full copies of potentially relevant studies were then obtained, either directly through the database concerned or through the University of Wollongong library. Even where relevant, studies where an abstract only was available were not included. Papers were then read in full and classified as: completely relevant, partially relevant or irrelevant accordingly. Irrelevant studies were discarded at this point. Those classified as partially relevant were retained in anticipation that more useful evidence might be obtained by alternative search methods, such as searching reference lists of other articles.

Data extraction and management

Data was extracted from selected studies using a standardized electronic data extraction form adapted from the public domain Cochrane Collaboration Data Collection Form for Intervention Review for RCT and Non-RCTs. Irrelevant sections were deleted, though the addition of sections was not required. The resultant form was then piloted using a few papers to ensure validity. The resultant data extraction form collected data on study design, participants, sample size, source, setting, response rate, risk of bias, results and conclusions. This information was then entered into a spreadsheet and organized alphabetically based on author's name.

Risk of bias assessment

Risk of bias in individual studies was assessed at the study level, utilizing The Cochrane Collaboration's tool for assessing risk of bias as a guide with any concerns regarding bias being recorded within the limitations section of the electronic data extraction form. This was done in accordance with the tool's six specific methodological areas for assessing bias: random sequence generation; allocation concealment; blinding of participants and personnel; blinding of outcome assessors; incomplete data and selective reporting. Sample size and response rate were recorded, along with whether randomization was used or not as a means to evaluate the generalizability of the contained studies. As this study is particularly interested in survey methods social desirability factors and self-reporting bias were also considered.

Summary measures

From the data recorded in the electronic data extraction form a summary of findings table has been constructed based upon the outcome measures. The GRADE (Grades of Recommendation, Assessment, Development and Evaluation) criteria was then applied to the summarized data to rate the quality of the evidence contained, especially in terms of internal and external validity (BMJ 2004). GRADE uses the following ratings for assessing the quality of evidence:

- High: consisting of randomized trials; or double-upgraded observational studies, where further research is unlikely to change confidence in research findings (BMJ 2004).
- Moderate: Downgraded randomized trials; or upgraded observational studies, where further research is likely to further reinforce or change our confidence in research findings (BMJ 2004).
- Low: Double-downgraded randomized trials; or observational studies, where further research will exert significant influence over our confidence in a set of research findings; possibly giving rise to changes in theory or practice (BMJ 2004).
- Very low: Triple-downgraded randomized trials; or downgraded observational studies; or case series/case reports, where further research into research findings is definitely required (BMJ 2004).

Primary database searches were summarized through the construction of a PRISMA flow diagram.

Synthesis of results

Data synthesis was conducted using narrative analysis to combine the findings of studies by identifying thematic consistencies (Ryan 2013). Studies were grouped together according to intervention type, study design and student health area (Ryan 2013). Comparisons were made between intervention and control conditions, where applicable, by looking at studies collectively (Ryan 2013). Narrative analysis was chosen due to the significant differences in the study designs and outcomes among included studies which made meta analysis impractical (Ryan 2013). Furthermore, information is captured from a wide range of interventions which cannot easily be pooled for statistical analysis (Ryan 2013). Therefore, results are presented descriptively, synergizing findings where appropriate, with tables being utilized as an aid to understanding the qualitative synthesis (Ryan 2013).

RESULTS

Study selection

Results of the search

Initial searching identified 25,141 potential studies for inclusion across 3 databases. Searching of ProQuest central was discontinued due to the large number of irrelevant results. A categorical search methodology was used to develop search terms for each individual health area. articles were then reviewed within each health category separately. This resulted in the following numbers of articles for each category:

Health Category	Number of Articles
Health care access	133
Sexual health	203
Mental health	596
Physical activity/nutrition	212
Substance use	217
TOTAL	1361

Table 1: Summary table of articles located according to student health category

Date range, full text and English language filters were applied to all of the above searches. Four articles were identified from other sources, specifically from bibliographies. Studies not from the UK, Australia, USA, Canada and New Zealand were then excluded. See Appendix 1: **PRISMA Study flow diagram** for detailed results of the literature search.

Included studies

In total, 54 individual studies were included in the final analysis consisting of 208,164 participants. For three studies sample size data was not specified (2 unspecified, 1 ongoing). Care was taken to ensure a balance of studies from across the identified health theme areas was represented in the final analysis. However, it was not possible to ensure equal numbers of studies for all health areas as this would have risked biasing the final results. Furthermore, number of articles obtained for each health area obviously varied according to the amount of research existent in a particular health area. The following numbers of articles were found for each health area:

- Health care access: $n= 10$
- Sexual health $n= 14$
- Mental health $n= 10$
- Physical activity/nutrition $n= 12$
- Substance use $n= 8$

For more detailed information regarding included studies, please consult Appendix 2: **Characteristics of included studies**. Excluded studies have not been tabulated due to the large number of results obtained.

Study designs

Of the 54 included studies thirty seven were observational studies of cross-sectional design (Arbour-Nicitopoulos et al. 2010; Balk et al. 2010; Bemel et al. 2015; Carmack et al. 2016; Chanakira et al. 2015; Dawson et al. 2007; DiStefano et al. 2013; D'Urso et al. 2007; Fagan 2007; Fogel et al. 2010; Funderburk et al. 2012; Garcia et al. 2010; Hallett et al. 2012; Han et al. 2015; Hardy et al. 2013; Holt et al. 2015; Hyun et al. 2007; King et al. 2014; Kingsbury et al. 2015; Kolodinsky et al. 2008; Kwan et al. 2013; Lombardi & Dupain 2014; Mackenzie et al. 2011; McCave et al. 2013; Miller et al. 2016; Milligan et al. 2014; Milhausen et al. 2013; Moore et al. 2012; Penwell-Waines et al. 2014; Pelletier & Laska 2013; Pootte et al. 2014; Rosenthal & Russell 2008; Shepardson & Funderburk 2014; Sontag-Padilla et al. 2015; Strawson et al. 2013; Wagner 2011; Walker et al. 2011; Wyatt & Oswald 2014). Five were randomized controlled trials (Kemmler et al. 2016; Moore et al. 2012; Reavley et al. 2014; Senn et al. 2015; Simmons & Brandon

2007). Two were longitudinal studies (Downs & Ashton 2011; LaChausse 2012). Two were case studies (Cimini et al. 2014; Goodhart et al. 2006). Five cohort designs were included, 4 retrospective (Denering & Spear 2012; Gaydos et al. 2010; Oswald et al. 2015; Varvil-Weld et al. 2013) and 1 prospective (Ullrich-French et al. 2013). Three field or community trials were included (Brown et al. 2014; Ehrhardt et al. 2006; Matthews et al. 2014).

Settings and participants

Thirty-nine studies were set in the United States (Balk et al. 2010; Bemel et al. 2015; Brown et al. 2014; Carmack et al. 2016; Cimini et al. 2014; Denering & Spear 2012; DiStefano et al. 2013; Downs & Ashton 2011; D'Urso et al. 2007; Ehrhardt et al. 2006; Han et al. 2015; Fagan 2007; Funderburk et al. 2012; Fogel et al. 2010; Gaydos et al. 2010; Goodhart et al. 2006; Hardy et al. 2013; Hyun et al. 2007; Kingsbury et al. 2015; King et al. 2014; Kolodinsky et al. 2008; LaChausse 2012; Lombardi & Dupain 2014; Mackenzie et al. 2011; McCave et al. 2013; Milligan et al. 2014; Miller et al. 2016; Moore et al. 2012; Oswald et al. 2015; Pelletier & Laska 2013; Penwell-Waines et al. 2014; Shepardson & Funderburk 2014; Senn et al. 2015; Simmons & Brandon 2007; Sontag-Padilla et al. 2015; Ullrich-French et al. 2013; Varvil-Weld et al. 2013; Wagner 2011; Walker et al. 2011; Wyatt & Oswald 2014). Eight were from Canada (Arbour-Nicitopoulos et al. 2010; Dawson et al. 2007; Garcia et al. 2010; Kwan et al. 2013; Matthews et al. 2014; Milhausen et al. 2013; Senn et al. 2015; Strawson et al. 2013). Four from the UK (Chanakira et al. 2015; Kemmler et al. 2016; Holt et al. 2015; Poote et al. 2014). Three were from Australia (Hallett et al. 2012; Reavley et al. 2014; Rosenthal & Russell 2008).

Study participants consisted of undergraduate students (Balk et al. 2010; Bemel et al. 2015; Brown et al. 2014; Dawson et al. 2007; DiStefano et al. 2013; Goodhart et al. 2006; Hallett et al. 2012; Kingsbury et al. 2015; LaChausse 2012; Lombardi & Dupain 2014; Moore et al. 2012; Ullrich-French et al. 2013; Varvil-Weld et al. 2013; Walker et al. 2011; Wyatt & Oswald 2014), combinations of undergraduates and postgraduates (Arbour-Nicitopoulos et al. 2010; Chanakira et al. 2015; Denering & Spear 2012; Downs & Ashton 2011; D'Urso et al. 2007; Ehrhardt et al. 2006; King et al. 2014; Kolodinsky et al. 2008; McCave et al. 2013; Milligan et al. 2014; Milhausen et al. 2013; Pelletier & Laska 2013; Wagner 2011), international students (Carmack et al. 2016; Rosenthal & Russell 2008), multi-university student samples (Hardy et al. 2013; Holt et al. 2015; Kwan et al. 2013; Oswald et al. 2015; Reavley et al. 2014; Senn et al. 2015; Sontag-Padilla et al. 2015), samples composed of staff and students (Cimini et al. 2014), university healthcare providers and patients (Fagan 2007; Funderburk et al. 2012; Mackenzie et al. 2011; Poote et al. 2014; Shepardson & Funderburk 2014),

students enrolled in specific subjects (Garcia et al. 2010; Han et al. 2015; Kemmler et al. 2016; Penwell-Waines et al. 2014; Strawson et al. 2013) and comparisons between students with differing characteristics (Fogel et al. 2010; Gaydos et al. 2010; Hyun et al. 2007; Miller et al. 2016; Simmons & Brandon 2007).

Interventions

All interventions included a survey element either delivered in the form of a questionnaire or focus groups (Carmack et al. 2016; Garcia et al. 2010; Kolodinsky et al. 2008). One study (Holt et al. 2015) combined both survey methods within a single cross-sectional study. Four studies used a pre-post test survey design (Brown et al. 2014; Downs & Ashton 2011; Ullrich-French et al. 2013; Varvil-Weld et al. 2013). One study consisted of an educational intervention targeting suicide risk among students (Cimini et al. 2014). Additionally educational interventions formed part of 6 other studies: Ehrhardt et al. (2006) implemented a peer led sexual health education program; Kingsbury et al. (2015) assessed the effectiveness of a harm minimization approach to alcohol used based upon social and health framing; LaChausse (2012) delivered internet based obesity education; Matthews et al. (2014) featured a nutrition education program based upon multi-sector partnerships which is still ongoing; Senn et al. (2015) conducted an RCT designed to measure the effectiveness of an innovative sexual assault education program; Simmons & Brandon (2007) also ran an RCT which used an experimental approach to secondary smoking prevention. Secondary analysis of existing survey and demographic data was undertaken in 3 studies (Denering & Spear 2012; Gaydos et al. 2010; Oswald et al. 2015). One study (Goodhart et al. 2006) functioned as a participant led research project. The RCT by Kemmler et al. (2016) documented biological measurements (BMI, VO2Max, Appendicular Skeletal Muscle Mass and Abdominal Fat Mass) related to body composition. Brief intervention techniques were the intervention of choice in the RCT by Moore et al. (2012) where three different brief interventions were compared in terms of to what degree sexual health knowledge and condom use increased. Furthermore, sexual health was the focus of the study by Milligan et al. (2014), in which an HIV testing intervention was piloted. Two studies (Reavley et al. 2014; Shepardson & Funderburk 2014) targeted mental health, Reavley et al. (2014) utilized a range of published resources combined with mental health first aid training within an RCT; while Shepardson & Funderburk (2014) implemented a mental health screening program.

Outcomes

Outcomes of individual studies are presented according to the previously identified thematic health categories.

Health care access

Bemel et al. (2015) identified that financial position had a significant impact on all measures of health and on propensity toward accessing required care. Similarly, the way in which health messages are delivered has a significant impact on how international students navigate the health system in the host country, as identified by Carmack et al. (2016). Additionally, Dawson et al. (2007) documented that attitudes towards positive and negative health behaviors varies significantly between genders, which needs to be taken into account when planning campus health services. Furthermore, Goodhart et al. (2006) underlined the need to directly involve students in the policy development process within institutions in order to develop a sense of student ownership over health promotion interventions and campus health services. Holt et al. (2015) reinforce this notion, that student health is multifactorial in nature and that university environments supportive of health play a significant role in determining the practice of healthy behaviour. Indeed, there appears to be a key need for more targeted health promotion campaigns which address multiple health issues (Kwan et al. 2013; Lombardi & Dupain 2014). Oswalt et al. (2015) also concluded that institutional characteristics correlate with health issues, with environmental characteristics having a significant impact upon health behavior. Findings by Poote et al. (2014) indicate that diversifying methods of healthcare delivery may improve uptake. Rosenthal & Russell (2008) found that a majority of students evaluate their health positively and that few international students found studying in a foreign country detrimental to their health.

Sexual health

Chanakira et al. (2015) found that a quarter of students survey reported engagement in high risk sexual practices. DiStefano et al. (2013) reported similar patterns, with 73% of students being sexually active in the past year while only 26% had been tested for HIV. D'Urso et al. (2007) determined that overall levels of STI awareness among students is low, especially in relation to Human Papillomavirus (HPV). The study by Ehrhardt et al. (2006) found that health promotion interventions do not necessarily decrease student sexual risk behavior, despite resulting in increased knowledge of sexual health issues. According to Fogel et al. (2010) ethnicity may play a role in propensity toward searching for sexual health information. Gaydos et al. (2010) also report that ethnic factors may influence rates of contraceptive use. McCave et al. (2013) consider more comprehensive reporting of student sexual health data to be necessary for the promotion of positive sexual health outcomes. Milligan et al. (2014) were able to combine reporting with screening, successfully facilitating HIV testing in a large number of previously untested people. Testing is essential if we consider the findings of Milhausen et al. (2013), detailing that less than half of students surveyed report consistent condom use and furthermore that when used the main consideration for their

use is prevention of unwanted pregnancy rather than STI infection. Moore et al (2012) found that the use of brief intervention techniques based upon real life scenarios resulted in increased knowledge gains in relation to safe sex, as did engagement with health workers from differing professional backgrounds (Penwell-Waines et al. 2014). Senn et al. (2015) conducted an RCT in which 1 year risk of sexual assault was significantly lower in the intervention than in the control group, resulting from an educational intervention. Wagner (2011) found that there was a possible association between marijuana use and likelihood of practicing safe sex, with those who had never used the substance being more likely to use condoms and to get tested for STIs. Wyatt & Oswalt (2014) observed that sexual risk was highest during the first year of undergraduate study.

Mental health

Balk et al. (2010) found that grief and loss associated with recent bereavement were significant issues for university students. Cimini et al. (2014) undertook an intervention program where individual awareness of suicide risk among peer groups was targeted within a single session format, resulting in temporary knowledge gains; though these were not sustained in the long term. Funderburk et al. (2012) provided data which demonstrates that a large proportion of poor mental health outcomes among students could potentially be mitigated by the implementation of primary behavioral health screening. Hardy et al. (2013) found that likelihood of engaging in risky health behavior is not directly mediated by mental health levels. Hyun et al. (2007) determined that international students tend to access on campus mental health services than their domestic student counterparts. In Mackenzie et al. (2011) it was observed that student depression is multifactorial and interrelated with other identified areas of student health such as sexual health and substance use. Reavley et al. (2014) conducted an RCT in which no effects on psychological distress and alcohol use were found, although overall mental health literacy was increased. Shepardson & Funderburk (2014) further developed the study of Funderburk et al. (2012) to further reinforce the need for on-campus mental health screening programs due to the interrelated nature of mental health with other dimensions of health. Sontag-Padilla et al. (2015) found that mental health diagnosis and care uptake rates among students were comparable. In common with the findings of Balk et al. (2010), Walker et al. (2011) determined grief to be a major cause of mental health issues among university students and equated it to a decline in academic performance.

Physical activity/nutrition

The field trial conducted by Brown et al. (2014) demonstrated that when students live within a health promoting community overall levels of physical activity increase. Downs

& Ashton (2011) documented that during transition to university physical activity levels decline markedly. Garcia et al. (2010) identified campus environment, nutrition knowledge, cost and time factors as major determinants of student dietary patterns. Han et al. (2015) evidenced that the transtheoretical model is useful in contextualizing student sedentary behaviour. Kemmler et al. (2016), like Downs & Ashton (2011) found that physical activity levels decline as an individual progresses through their academic career. Data from King et al. (2014) indicate that students are more likely to continue physical activity once in a higher education environment if they are members of a peer group in which other members are active exercisers. The findings of Kolodinsky et al. (2008) suggest that students are health conscious when making food purchases from on-campus outlets. LaChausse (2012) conducted an educational intervention which succeeded in improving the practice of healthy eating, but had little effect on physical activity levels. The ongoing study by Matthews et al. (2014) is also showing improvements in nutritional knowledge resulting from intervention. Pelletier & Laska (2013) determined that those who purchased food on campus tended to eat less healthily than those who brought food from home. This is in line with the findings of Strawson et al. (2013) which found that a majority of students didn't meet dietary guidelines. Ullrich-French et al. (2013) corroborate a majority of the former findings in that physical activity decreased during the transition from high school to university.

Substance use

Arbour-Nicitopoulos et al. (2010) recorded that 70% of students regularly use alcohol, with smoking and marijuana use being present in 15% of respondents. Denering & Spear (2012) found that brief intervention techniques were useful in reducing problematic cannabis and alcohol use. Fagan (2007) identified the need to increase practitioner self-efficacy for undertaking smoking cessation counselling. Hallett et al. (2012) record that prevalence of alcohol use among students was very high and that more than a third regularly drank at hazardous levels. In the intervention study by Kingsbury et al. (2015) effectiveness of alcohol education was improved by framing alcohol use in terms of the negative social consequences associated with it rather than just the health effects. Miller et al. (2016) impart that students significantly underestimate the effects of binge drinking in terms of individual intake. Simmons & Brandon (2007) conducted an experimental smoking cessation intervention which proved more effective than standard approaches to smoking cessation, though only in the case of females. Varvil-Weld et al. (2013) ascertained that parental permissiveness was consistently and positively associated with college drinking.

Risk of bias in included studies

Sufficient information regarding potential bias within included studies was obtained from the data extraction process, due to time constraints individual authors were not contacted. A majority of studies contained within this review are of an observational design, limiting their individual ability to be generalized to other populations; though when combined as has been done here, applicability is increased somewhat. This is possible due the relatively tight selection criteria utilized, which facilitate the construction of a homogenous population across multiple studies. Seven studies suffered from a low response rate (<30%) (Arbour-Nicitopoulos et al. 2010; Balk et al. 2010; Bemel et al. 2015; Chanakira et al. 2015; Funderburk et al. 2012; Lombardi & Dupain 2014; McCave et al. 2013), raising the possibility of non-response bias. Furthermore, sixteen studies, despite containing a survey element did not specify their response rate (Cimini et al. 2014; Downs & Ashton 2011; D'Urso et al. 2007; Han et al. 2015; Hardy et al. 2013; Kingsbury et al. 2015; Miller et al. 2016; Milligan et al. 2014; Milhausen et al. 2013; Pelletier & Laska 2013; Poote et al. 2014; Shepardson & Funderburk 2014; Sontag-Padilla et al. 2015; Ullrich-French et al. 2013; Wagner 2011; Walker et al. 2011). A lack of randomization was evident in a large number of studies increasing the potential for selection bias to arise. Randomization was only employed in 8 out of 54 studies (Arbour-Nicitopoulos et al. 2010; Kemmler et al. 2016; Kingsbury et al. 2015; McCave et al. 2013; Moore et al. 2012; Reavley et al. 2014; Senn et al. 2015; Simmons & Brandon 2007).

Effects of interventions

Intervention effects are presented in terms of the outcome measures set out at the beginning of the review process as a series of bullet points. Not all studies included separate intervention and control groups. Additionally, some studies recorded effects on health of certain environmental conditions, rather than improvement effects of intervention.

Self-reported improvement in health as a result of intervention

- Gender sensitive planning of health promotion programs increases their effectiveness (Dawson et al. 2007).
- Students reported improvements in mental health after involvement in integrated behavioral health programs (Funderburk et al. 2012).
- Improved motivation and self-efficacy to make nutrition related changes occurred through the use of the photowise approach (Garcia et al. 2010).
- The use of photowise methods empowered students to take more responsibility for their health (Goodhart et al. 2006).

- The transtheoretical model is effective in helping students make individual improvements to their health (Han et al. 2015).
- Those delivering peer-led nutrition education experienced overall increases in health-related self-efficacy (Matthews et al. 2014).
- A properly designed sexual assault education program is effective in reducing occurrence of sexual assault even in women previously subjected (Senn et al. 2015).
- Experimental theory based intervention and standard didactic smoking cessation advice resulted in comparable levels of self reported smoking cessation at 1 month follow up (Simmons & Brandon 2007).

Decrease in risky behavior, as appropriate to health category

- When living in a health promoting environment overall levels of student physical activity increase (Brown et al. 2014).
- Suicide risk among students was significantly reduced through the use of a single session educational program (Cimini et al. 2014).
- Brief intervention techniques are effective in reducing hazardous substance use (Denering & Spear 2012).
- Previous subjection to sexual violence functions as a major prompt to seek an HIV test (DiStefano et al. 2013).
- Peer-led sexual health education programs did not result in a decrease in risky sexual behavior (Ehrhardt et al. 2006).
- Ethnically targeted contraceptive counselling may be effective in increasing condom use (Gaydos et al. 2010).
- Framing alcohol use in terms of potential negative social consequences resulted in a decrease in high-risk patterns of alcohol use (Kingsbury et al. 2015).
- Internet based nutrition education programs increase fruit and vegetable consumption among students, but have no effect on physical activity levels (LaChausse 2012).
- Campus based HIV testing increases the number of persons taking tests and may prompt reevaluation of sexual risk (Milligan et al. 2014).
- Using pictures of STIs combined with hearing about real life experiences had a positive effect in decreasing sexual risk post-intervention (Moore et al. 2012).
- Use of computerized self assessment platforms improved individual responsibility for health (Poote et al. 2014).
- Personalization of interventions reduces mental health risk (Reavley et al. 2014).
- Behavioral health screening in a university health center can help identify students with behavioral health concerns and increase access to care (Shepardson & Funderburk 2014)

- Secondary prevention based intervention improves smoking cessation outcomes within female participants (Simmons & Brandon 2007).
- Focussing prevention education on parents results in reduced student drinking (Varvil-Weld et al. 2013).
- Health education on safe sex from healthcare providers results in more STI testing than when information is obtained from alternative sources (Wagner 2011).

Increase in health literacy as a result of intervention

- Changing the format in which health messages are delivered has a positive effect in improving the health of international students (Carmack et al. 2016).
- Knowledge levels of suicide awareness decreased significantly 3 months when followed up 3 month post-intervention (Cimini et al. 2014).
- Improvements in health literacy in relation to substance use resulting from the use of brief intervention are retained nearly a year later (Denering & Spear 2012).
- Combining HIV testing with education around sexual violence may facilitate better resistance to sexual assault among young women (DiStefano et al. 2013).
- Improvements in HPV awareness occur as a result of interaction with healthcare providers (D'Urso et al. 2007).
- Involvement in a peer education program improved overall knowledge of sexual risk (Ehrhardt et al. 2006).
- Use of the photowise approach improved nutrition related health literacy (Garcia et al. 2010).
- The transtheoretical model is effective, when used as part of a health intervention program at increasing health literacy (Han et al. 2015).
- Peer-led nutrition education improved general nutrition knowledge (Matthews et al. 2014).
- Having an individual in charge of the learning process improved sexual health knowledge (Moore et al. 2012).
- Interprofessional approaches to sexual health education are effective in preparing students from diverse health disciplines to navigate the wider sexual health environment (Penwell-Waines et al. 2014).
- Education and awareness may play a role in improving mental health literacy (Reavley et al. 2014).

DISCUSSION

Summary of main results

Clearly a decline is taking place in student health during transition to university, which continues throughout the undergraduate study (Downs & Ashton 2011; Wyatt & Oswalt 2014). This is particularly evident in regard to reduced physical activity and an increased uptake in poor dietary patterns (Downs & Ashton 2011; Kemmler et al. 2016; Strawson et al. 2013). Those who maintain higher levels of physical activity appear better able to cope with and offset the mental and physical health consequences of this abrupt transition (Downs & Ashton 2011; Kemmler et al. 2016). Transition to university from secondary education appears to be a particularly traumatic experience for students, with many experiencing some degree of loss which can affect academic performance (Balk et al. 2010; Walker et al. 2011). Furthermore, individual risk of suicide also appears to increase during this time, possibly resulting from experiencing some degree of grief, bereavement or loss (Balk et al. 2010; Cimini et al. 2014; Walker et al. 2011). This is of particular concern for international students as their appears to be an unmet mental health need among international students requiring services to be made more culturally appropriate (Hyun et al. 2007). Moreover, despite appearing to not directly increase propensity to engage in risky behavior, those with unmanaged emotional health issues appear to be more likely to report previous engagement in risky sexual practices, substance use and subjection to emotional abuse (Hardy et al. 2013; Mackenzie et al. 2011; Shepardson & Funderburk 2014).

Sexual health is another area of concern, with many students not being adequately prepared to navigate risk, with overall levels of STI awareness being low (Chanakira et al. 2015; DiStefano et al. 2013; D'Urso et al. 2007; Wyatt & Oswalt 2014). Additionally, multiple sources indicate that despite sex education at the secondary level many a large proportion of students lack self efficacy in the application of safe sex (Gaydos et al. 2010; McCave et al. 2013; Milhausen et al. 2013). A significant proportion of female students also report being subject to some degree of sexual violence, with assault and coercion being relatively common in some student populations (DiStefano et al. 2013).

Substance use, particularly bingeing appears relatively common, with the main agents of choice being alcohol and tobacco. Additionally, experimentation with illegal drugs is relatively common though less evidence exists for the widespread use of narcotics, although the prevalence of marijuana use is appears higher among students than other populations (Denering & Spear 2012). Drugs and alcohol also often function as a form of self-medication among student populations (Denering & Spear 2012; Hardy et al. 2013). Especially for more acute mental health problems such as those associated with

depression stress and anxiety (Denering & Spear 2012). Such a pattern is particularly prevalent where students lack access to good on campus counselling services (Denering & Spear 2012; Funderburk et al. 2012; Reavley et al. 2014; Sontag-Padilla et al. 2015).

Student health services or campaigns can only be correctly planned and rendered efficacious by containing multiple elements which target a number of health conditions or variables synergistically (Holt et al. 2015; Kwan et al. 2013; Lombardi & Dupain 2014). Self-efficacy for accessing health care services among students appears to be largely determined by level of individual health literacy (LaChausse 2012; Matthews et al. 2014). Additionally, campuses need to be ran as health promoting environments so that changes brought about by intervention programs can be sustained in the long term (Brown et al. 2014; Garcia et al. 2010). Indeed, if resources and infrastructure are available which promote health students are more likely to engage in health-enhancing behavior such as exercise (King et al. 2014; Kolodinsky et al. 2008; Pelletier & Laska 2013). Gender appears to be a factor as well, therefore campus health care programs need to be sensitive to gender differences and at the same time promote access for international students (Carmack et al. 2016; Hyun et al. 2007; Simmons & Brandon 2007).

Limitations

A lack of diversity is present in the source populations of this study, everyone being involved in the university community in some way, either as students, faculty or healthcare providers. Therefore, the generalizability of these findings may be limited. A significant proportion of the material featured consists of data drawn from observational studies, which are towards the lower end of the evidential hierarchy. Potential bias may also have arisen from the review process in that the literature was reviewed by a single reviewer only.

Conclusions

University students are a population at increased risk of poor health. Aspects of mental health are central to the health continuum of university students, acting as a mediating factor affecting risk in relation to other areas of health.

Implications for practice

Health promotion aimed at university student populations needs to be planned to take into account the multifactorial nature of student health. Programs need to be targeted to address multiple aspects of health within a single intervention to maximise the impact of health improvement and cost effectiveness. Additionally, consulting with stakeholders

during the research and development process is essential to develop a sense of ownership, improve health-related self-efficacy and to facilitate sustainability.

Implications for future research

Currently, there is a tendency within research to view the various areas of student health in isolation. A paradigm shift within student related health research is necessary to take into account how conditions affecting student health outcomes are interrelated. This includes capturing more data on the interaction between health and features of the campus environment.

REFERENCES

- Arbour-Nicitopoulos, K, Kwan, M, Lowe, D, Taman, S & Faulkner, G 2010, 'Social norms of alcohol, smoking and marijuana use within a Canadian university setting', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 191-196.
- Balk, D, Walker, A & Baker, A 2010, 'Prevalence and severity of college student bereavement examined in a randomly selected sample', *Death Studies*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 459-468.
- Bemel, J, Brower, C, Chilschille, A & Shepherd, J 2015, 'The Impact of College Student Financial Health on Other Dimensions of Health', *American Journal of Health Promotion*, Published Electronically on July 9th 2015.
- Brown, D, Bray, S, Beatty, K & Kwan, M 2014, 'Healthy Active Living: A Residence Community–Based Intervention to Increase Physical Activity and Healthy Eating During the Transition to First-Year University', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 234-242.
- British Medical Journal (BMJ) 2004, 'Grading quality of evidence and strength of recommendations', *British Medical Journal*, vol. 328, no. 7454, pp. 1490-1494.
- Carmack, H, Bedi, S & Heiss, S 2016, 'International Students, University Health Centres, and Memorable Messages about Health', *Journal of International Students*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 52-72.
- Chanakira, E, Goyder, E, Freeman, J, O'Cathain, A, Kinghorn, G & Jakubovic, M 2015, 'Social and psychosocial factors associated with high-risk sexual behaviour among university students in the United Kingdom: a web-survey', *International Journal of STD and AIDS*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 369-378.

Cimini, M, Rivero, E, Bernier, J, Stanley, J, Murray, A, Anderson, D, Wright, H & Bapat, M 2014, 'Implementing an audience-specific small-group gatekeeper training program to respond to suicide risk among college students: a case study', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 62, no.2, pp. 92-100.

Dawson, K, Schneider, M, Fletcher, P & Bryden, P 2007, 'Examining gender differences in health Behaviors of Canadian university students', *Perspectives in Public Health*, vol. 127, no. 1, pp. 38-44.

Denering, L & Spear, S 2012, 'Routine Use of Screening and Brief Intervention for College Students in a University Counseling Center', *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 318-324.

DiStefano, A, Gill, J, Hubach, R, Caytano, R & Hilbert, C 2013, 'HIV testing in an ethnically diverse sample of American university students: associations with violence/abuse and covariates', *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 1030-1046.

Downs, A & Ashton, J 2011, 'Vigorous Physical Activity, Sports Participation, and Athletic Identity: Implications for Mental and Physical Health in College Students', *Journal of Sport Behavior*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 228-249.

D'Urso, J, Thompson-Robinson, M & Chandler, S 2007, 'HPV knowledge and behaviors of black college students at a historically black university', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 159-163.

Ehrhardt, B, Krumboltz, J & Koopman, C 2007, 'Training Peer Sexual Health Educators: Changes in Knowledge, Counseling Self-Efficacy, and Sexual Risk Behavior', *American Journal of Sexuality Education*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 39-55.

Fagan, K 2007, 'Smoking-cessation counseling practices of college/university health-care providers--a theory-based approach', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 351-360.

Fogal, J, Fajiram, S & Morgan, P 2010, 'Sexual Health Information Seeking on the Internet: Comparisons between White and African American College Students', *ABNF Journal*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 79-84.

Funderburk, J, Fielder, R, DeMartini, K & Flynn, C 2012, 'Integrating behavioral health services into a university health center: patient and provider satisfaction', *Families, Systems & Health*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 130-140.

Garcia, A, Sykes, L, Matthews, J, Martin, N & Leipert, B 2010, 'Perceived facilitators of and barriers to healthful eating among university students', *Canadian Journal of Dietetic Practice & Research*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 28-33.

Gaydos, L, Neubert, B, Hogue, C, Kramer, M & Yang, Z 2010, 'Racial disparities in contraceptive use between student and nonstudent populations', *Journal of Women's Health*, vol.19, no. 3, pp. 589-595.

Goodhart, F, Hsu, J, Baek J, Coleman, A, Maresca, F & Miller, M 2006, 'A view through a different lens: photovoice as a tool for student advocacy', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 53-56.

Hallett, J, Howat, P, Maycock, B, McManus, A, Kypri, K & Dhaliwal, S 2012, 'Undergraduate student drinking and related harms at an Australian university: web-based survey of a large random sample', *BMC Public Health*, vol. 12, pp. 37.

Han, H, Gabriel, K, & Kohl, H 2015, 'Evaluations of Validity and Reliability of a Transtheoretical Model for Sedentary Behavior among College Students', *American Journal of Health Behavior*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 601-609.

Hardy, S, Francis, S, Zamboanga, B, Kim, S, Anderson, S & Forthun, L 2013, 'The Roles of Identity Formation and Moral Identity in College Student Mental Health, Health-risk Behaviors, and Psychological Well-Being', *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, vol. 69, no. 4, pp. 364-382.

Holt, M, Monk, R, Powell, S & Dooris, M 2015, 'Student perceptions of a healthy university', *Public Health*, vol. 129, no. 6, pp. 674-683.

Hyun, J, Quinn, B, Madon, T & Lustig, S 2007, 'Mental health need, awareness, and use of counseling services among international graduate students', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 56, no. 1, 2, pp. 109-118.

Kemmler, W, von Stengl, S, Kohl, M & Baur, J 2016, 'Impact of exercise changes on body composition during the college years -a five year randomized controlled study', *BMC Public Health*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 50.

King, K, Vidourek, R, English, L & Merianos, A 2014, 'Vigorous physical activity among college students: using the health belief model to assess involvement and social support', *Archives of Exercise in Health & Disease*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 251-280.

Kingsbury, J, Gibbons, F & Gerrard, M 2015, 'The effects of social and health consequence framing on heavy drinking intentions among college students', *British Journal of Health Psychology*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 212-220.

Kolodinsky, J, Green, J, Michahelles, M & Harvey-Berino, J 2008, 'The use of nutritional labels by college students in a food-court setting', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 297-301.

Kwan, M, Faulkner, G, Arbour-Nicitopoulos, K & Cairney, J 2013, 'Prevalence of health-risk behaviours among Canadian post-secondary students: descriptive results from the National College Health Assessment', *BMC Public Health*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1-6.

LaChausse, R 2012, 'My Student Body: Effects of an Internet-Based Prevention Program to Decrease Obesity Among College Students', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 60, no. 4, pp. 324-330.

Lombardi, J & Dupain, M 2014, 'Assessment and evaluation of student health behaviors at a state-supported regional university', *American Journal of Health Studies*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 205-214.

Mackenzie, S, Wiegel, J, Mundt, M, Brown, D, Saewyc, E, Heiligenstein, E, Harahan, B & Fleming, M 2011, 'Depression and suicide ideation among students accessing campus health care', *The American Journal Of Orthopsychiatry*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 101-107.

Matthews, J, Zok, A, Quenneville, E & Dworatzek, P 2014, 'Development and implementation of FRESH--a post-secondary nutrition education program incorporating population strategies, experiential learning and intersectoral partnerships', *Canadian Journal of Public Health*, vol. 105, no. 11, pp. 306-311.

McCave, E, Azulay Chertok, I, Winter, V & Haile, Z 2013, 'Sexual health behaviors in a random sample of students at a Mid-Atlantic university: 2010-2011', *Journal of Community Health*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 310-319.

Milhausen, R, McKay, A, Graham, C, Crosby, R, Yarber, W & Sanders, S 2013, 'Prevalence and predictors of condom use in a national sample of Canadian university students', *Canadian Journal of Human Sexuality*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 142-151.

Miller, M, Brett, E, Leavens, E, Meier, E, Borsari, B & Leffingwell, T 2016, 'Informing alcohol interventions for student service members/veterans: Normative perceptions and coping strategies', *Addictive Behaviors*, vol. 57, pp. 76-82.

Milligan, C, Cueno, C, Rutstein, S & Hicks, C 2014, "Know Your Status": results from a novel, student-run HIV testing initiative on college campuses, *AIDS Education and Prevention*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 317-327.

Moore, E, Smith, W & Folsom, A 2012, 'F.O.R.E.play: the utility of brief sexual health interventions among college students', *Journal of American College Health*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 175-177.

Oswalt, S, Lederer, A & Schrader, L 2015, 'Institutional Characteristics and the Connection to College Student Health', *American Journal of Health Behavior*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 475-486.

Pelletier, J & Laska, M 2013, 'Campus food and beverage purchases are associated with indicators of diet quality in college students living off campus', *American Journal of Health Promotion*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 80-87.

Penwell-Waines, L, Wilson, C, Macapagal, K, Valvano, A, Waller, J, West, L & Stepleman, L 2014, 'Student perspectives on sexual health: implications for interprofessional education', *Journal of Interprofessional Care*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 317-322.

Poote, A, French, D, Dale, J & Powell, J 2014, 'A study of automated self-assessment in a primary care student health centre setting', *Journal of Telemedicine and Telecare*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 123-127.

Reavley, N, McCann, T, Cvetkovski, S & Jorm A 2014, 'A multifaceted intervention to improve mental health literacy in students of a multicampus university: a cluster randomised trial', *Social Psychiatry And Psychiatric Epidemiology*, vol. 49, no. 10, pp. 1655-1666.

Rosenthal, D, Russell, J & Thompson, G 2008, 'The health and wellbeing of international students at an Australian university', *Higher Education*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 51-67.

Ryan, R 2013, *Cochrane Consumers and Communication Review Group: data synthesis and analysis*, Cochrane Consumers and Communication Review Group, Oxford.

Senn, C, Eliasziw, M, Barata, P, Thurston, W, Newby-Clark, I & Hobden, K 2015, 'Efficacy of a Sexual Assault Resistance Program for University Women', *New England Journal of Medicine*, vol. 372, no. 24, pp. 2326-2335.

Shepardson, R & Funderburk, J 2014, 'Implementation of universal behavioral health screening in a university health setting', *Journal of Psychology in Medical Settings*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 253-266.

Simmons, V & Brandon, T 2007, 'Secondary smoking prevention in a university setting: a randomized comparison of an experiential, theory-based intervention and a standard didactic intervention for increasing cessation motivation.', *Health Psychology*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 268-277.

Sontag-Padilla, L, Woodbridge, M, Mendelsohn, J, D'Amico, E, Osilla, K, Jaycox, L, Eberhart, N, Burnam, A & Stein, B 2016, 'Factors Affecting Mental Health Service Utilization Among California Public College and University Students', *Psychiatric Services*, Ahead of print.

Strawson, T, Bell, R, Downs, S, Farmer, A, Olstad, D & Willows, N 2013, 'Dietary patterns of female university students with nutrition education', *Canadian Journal of Dietetic Practice and Research*, vol. 74, no. 3, pp. 138-142.

Ullrich-French, S, Cox, A & Bumpus M 2013, 'Physical activity motivation and behavior across the transition to university', *Sport, Exercise and Performance Psychology*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 90-101.

Varvil-Weld, L, Crowley, D, Turrisi, R, Greenberg, M & Mallett, K 2014, 'Hurting, helping, or neutral? The effects of parental permissiveness toward adolescent drinking on college student alcohol use and problems', *Prevention Science*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 716-724.

Wagner, W 2011, 'Source of Safe Sex Knowledge and Sexual Behavior Among University Students', *Californian Journal of Health Promotion*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 25-35.

Walker, A, Hathcoat, J & Noppe, I 2011, 'College student bereavement experience in a Christian university', *Journal of Death and Dying*, vol. 64, no. 3, pp. 241-259.

Wyatt, T & Oswald, S 2014, 'Sexual Behaviors of College Freshmen and the Need for University-Based Education', *College Student Journal*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 603-612.

Appendix 1: PRISMA Study flow diagram

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

From: Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, The PRISMA Group (2009). Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement. PLoS Med 6(7): e1000097. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed1000097

For more information, visit www.prisma-statement.org.

Appendix 2: Characteristics of included studies

Health care access

Reference	Country	Study Design	Intervention	Subjects	Sample Size	GRADE Rating
Bemel et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate students	3000	Low
Carmack et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Focus groups	International students	21	Low
Dawson et al.	Canada	Cross-sectional	Survey	Male and female undergraduate students	638	Low
Goodhart et al.	USA	Case study	Participant led research project	Undergraduate students	-	Very low
Holt et al.	UK	Cross-sectional	Survey/focus groups	Students from 11 UK universities	423	Low
Kwan et al.	Canada	Cross-sectional	Survey	Randomly sampled students from 8 canadian post-secondary institutions	8182	Moderate
Lombardi & Dupain	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate students	1019	Low
Oswalt et al.	USA	Retrospective cohort	Secondary data analysis	Undergraduate students	81242	Moderate
Poote et al.	UK	Cross-sectional	Survey	Patients at a university health centre	201	Low
Rosenthal & Russell	Australia	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate and postgraduate international students	979	Low

Sexual health

Reference	Country	Study Design	Intervention	Subjects	Sample Size	GRADE Rating
Chanakira et al.	UK	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate and postgraduate students	3511	Low
DiStefano et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Ethnically diverse	1210	Low

				undergraduate students		
D'Urso et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate and postgraduate students	351	Low
Ehrhardt et al.	USA	Community trial	Peer-led sexual health program	Undergraduate and postgraduate students	70	Moderate
Fogel et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	African american and white undergraduate college students	149	Low
Gaydos et al.	USA	Retrospective cohort	Secondary data analysis	African American students and non-students	20632	Moderate
McCave et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	A stratified random sample of undergraduate and graduate students	2304	Moderate
Milligan et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Testing intervention with optional survey element	Private university and community college students	1408 HIV tests were conducted	Moderate
Milhausen et al.	Canada	Cross-sectional	Survey	Canadian university students aged 18 to 24	1500	Low
Moore et al.	USA	RCT	1 of 3 brief interventions with pre-post survey	First year university students	302	High
Penwell-Waines et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey with secondary educational intervention	University students	472	Moderate
Senn et al.	Canada	RCT	Educational intervention	First-year female students	893	High
Wagner, W	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	University students	541	Low
Wyatt & Oswalt	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	First year university students	433	Low

Mental health

Reference	Country	Study Design	Intervention	Subjects	Sample Size	GRADE Rating
Balk et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate students	433	Low
Cimini et al.	USA	Case study	Educational intervention	Faculty, staff and students	335	Very low
Funderburk et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Providers and patients at a university health centre	288	Low
Hardy et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Students aged 18-25 years from 31 universities	9500	Low
Hyun et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	International graduate students and domestic students	3121	Low
Mackenzie et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Students using a university health clinic	1622	Low
Reavley et al.	Australia	RCT	Publication based interventions	Students from a large multi-campus university	767	High
Shepardson & Funderburk	USA	Cross-sectional	Mental health screening program	University students accessing a campus health centre	-	Low
Sontag-Padilla et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	University staff and students	47961	Moderate
Walker et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate students at a Christian university	442	Low

Physical activity/nutrition

Reference	Country	Study Design	Intervention	Subjects	Sample Size	GRADE Rating
Brown et al.	USA	Field trial	Residence-based physical activity intervention with pre-post survey	Undergraduate students	60	Moderate
Downs &	USA	Longitudinal	Pre-post test	Male and	395	Moderate

Ashton			experiment	female students		
Garcia et al.	Canada	Cross-sectional	Focus groups	Undergraduate students	28	Low
Han et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Students aged 18-25 years on physical education courses	225	Low
Kemmler et al.	UK	RCT	Biological measurements with periodic survey	Randomly selected dental and physical education students	114	High
King et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	University students	480	Low
Kolodinsky et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	College aged students	16	Very low
LaChausse, R	USA	Longitudinal	Internet based educational program, with on campus program as control intervention	Undergraduate students	320	Moderate
Matthews et al.	Canada	Community trial	Educational intervention	Undergraduate students enrolled in nutrition subjects, with other university community members as project beneficiaries	Ongoing	Moderate
Pelletier & Laska	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Students living off-campus	1059	Low
Strawson et al.	Canada	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate nutrition students	40	Low
Ullrich-French et al.	USA	Prospective cohort	Survey	Incoming undergraduate students	382	High

Substance use

Reference	Country	Study Design	Intervention	Subjects	Sample Size	GRADE Rating
Arbour-Nicitopoulos et al.	Canada	Cross-sectional	Survey	Randomly sampled students	1203	Low

Denering & Spear	USA	Retrospective cohort	Secondary data analysis	Students aged 18-24	453	Moderate
Fagan, K	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Health care providers	296	Low
Hallett et al.	Australia	Cross-sectional	Survey	Randomly selected undergraduate students	7237	Moderate
Kingsbury et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Undergraduate students	124	Low
Miller et al.	USA	Cross-sectional	Survey	Civilian and military students	319	Low
Simmons & Brandon	USA	RCT	Experimental smoking cessation intervention	Smoking college students	215	High
Varvil-Weld et al.	USA	Retrospective cohort	Survey	First year undergraduate students	1518	Moderate